

1 **BCAT1 is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.**

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6 Glioblastoma is difficult to treat and patients are often provided poor prognosis (1), indicating a
7 requirement for therapeutic target identification and drug development. Differentially expressed genes
8 represent by definition among the most promising targets for the development of novel chemotherapies (2,
9 3). We predict therapeutic index is intrinsically linked to differential expression which can be
10 comprehensively and blindly determined using whole transcriptome data, further limiting toxicity by
11 design (4). We mined published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify
12 differentially expressed gene products in glioblastoma by performing whole transcriptome gene expression
13 profiling. We found that the gene encoding the anti-silencing function 1B histone chaperone, BCAT1, was
14 among those whose expression was most different in human glioblastoma tumors when comparing total
15 transcription between tumor and normal brain tissue. BCAT1 expression levels were significantly
16 increased in glioblastoma tumors as compared to the non-transformed brain. BCAT1 function at the
17 systems level was assessed by studying whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation in the
18 transformed brain. BCAT1 is a target of interest for the treatment of glioblastoma, as part of a rationally
19 designed chemotherapeutic regimen that utilizes gene expression data from patient tumors and healthy
20 non-transformed tissues to maximize efficacy and safety and minimize toxicity.

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26 Keywords: BCAT1, anti-silencing function 1B histone chaperone, glioblastoma, systems biology of
27 glioblastoma, targeted therapeutics in glioblastoma.

1 Brain cancer encompasses a spectrum of solid tumors that affect the brain in children and adults
2 including medulloblastoma, neuroblastoma, and glioblastoma (7). Rational development of targeted
3 therapeutics to treat patients with glioblastoma can be supported by an enhanced understanding of
4 fundamental transcriptional differences that define the glioblastoma tumor. To discover genes associated
5 with glioblastoma in humans in an unbiased fashion and at the systems level, we compared total
6 transcription in the normal brain and in the glioblastoma tumor using published and public human
7 glioblastoma microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify a molecular signature or fingerprint
8 of glioblastoma, among the most lethal and difficult to treat solid tumors affecting adults. We describe
9 here identification of a potential therapeutic target in glioblastoma based on quantitative whole
10 transcriptome methods.

11 **Methods**

12 We utilized microarray datasets GSE116520 (5) and GSE184643 (6) for this differential gene
13 expression analysis of the brain cancer glioblastoma in humans using R-based computational methods
14 (GEO2R). GSE116520 was generated using Illumina HumanHT-12 V4.0 expression beadchip
15 technology; for this analysis, we used $n=8$ control brain tissue and $n=17$ glioblastoma tumors, and the
16 analysis was performed using platform GPL10558. GSE184643 was generated using Illumina NovaSeq
17 6000 (Homo sapiens) technology; for this analysis, we used $n=3$ control brain tissue and $n=3$ glioblastoma
18 tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL24676. All tumors utilized for differential
19 gene expression analysis here were of the adenocarcinoma type. The Benjamini and Hochberg method of
20 p-value adjustment was used for ranking of differential expression but raw p-values were used to assess
21 statistical significance of global differential expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and
22 the NCBI generated category of platform annotation was used. SEEK was utilized for transcriptional
23 co-regulation studies (8).

24 **Results**

25 We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technologies and cross-laboratory validation (5, 6)
26 to discover in an unbiased fashion and at the transcriptome level the most distinguishing gene expression
27 features of the human brain cancer glioblastoma.

28 BCAT1 is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.

1. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with glioblastoma

$n=8$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=17$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1695414	8.13E-07	-5.7960359	5.528856	-1.45637301	BCAT1	3168/47229	93.3

29 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma
30 tumor tissue, we discovered differential expression of anti-silencing function 1B histone chaperone,
31 encoded by BCAT1 in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of BCAT1 changed more than
32 90% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression
33 was measured - in this case, 47,229 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change

1 indicating increased quantity of BCAT1 messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating
2 up-regulation of BCAT1 during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

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4 2. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with brain cancer: glioblastoma.

5 $n=3$ normal brain tissues (human)

6 $n=3$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

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ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
55723	8.80E-09	0.582	-5.752415	-3.34581869	122.07	BCAT1	515/19678	97.4

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9 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma
10 tumors in a second RNA-sequencing dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort,
11 we validated differential expression of BCAT1 in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of
12 BCAT1 here changed more than 95% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering
13 all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,678 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the
14 negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of BCAT1 messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors,
15 demonstrating up-regulation of BCAT1 during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to
16 glioblastoma.

17 Thus, BCAT1 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the
18 glioblastoma subtype in humans.

19 BCAT1 transcriptional co-regulation.

20 Finally, we utilized a separate systems methodology that utilizes whole transcriptome data to
21 provide insight into molecular function of a gene product by evaluating the transcriptional network within
22 which it operates through identification of co-regulated gene partners.

1 In the transformed brain, BCAT1 was transcriptionally co-regulated with IL1RAP, IKBIP CTHRC1
2 and TNFAIP6.

3 Thus, blind comparative transcriptome analysis of glioblastomas revealed differential expression of
4 BCAT1 as among the most significant transcriptional features of glioblastoma tumors; systems level query
5 into BCAT1 molecular function across multiple tissues at the transcriptome level revealed its co-regulation
6 with IL1RAP, IKBIP, CTHRC1 and TNFAIP6.

6 **Discussion**

7 We found by mining published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) that the
8 anti-silencing function 1B histone chaperone, BCAT1, was among the genes most differentially expressed
9 in the primary tumors of patients with glioblastoma; BCAT1 was expressed at significantly higher levels in
10 glioblastoma tumors as compared to the brain. BCAT1 is a target of interest for rationally designed
11 medical treatment of glioblastoma, a difficult to treat adult solid tumor.
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